

```

/**** TABLE 1 - selected OU models and simple linear reg for TZ using nlmixed. **/
/** READ IN THE RAW DATA **/
FILENAME REFFILE '/folders/myfolders/TZallchildrenSAS.csv';
PROC IMPORT DATAFILE=REFFILE
  DBMS=CSV
  OUT=work.TZ
  replace;
  datarow=2;
  GETNAMES=YES;
  guessingrows=MAX;
RUN;
PROC CONTENTS DATA=WORK.TZ; RUN;

/** check that subjects are sorted - essential for RVs **/
proc sort data=TZ out=TZ;
by subjid;
run;

ods html5 file='/folders/myfolders/SI2output.html';

/** FIXED EFFECT OU */
proc nlmixed data=TZ;
  parms sigma2=10 theta=5 mu=0.5;
  mean = exp((-agectsl+agectso)*theta)*(zwfl0-mu) + mu;
  var=(exp(-2*agectsl*theta)*( exp(2*agectsl*theta) -exp(2*agectso*theta) ) *sigma2)/(2*theta);
  model zwfl1 ~ normal(mean,var);
run;

/** LINEAR REGRESSION */
proc nlmixed data=TZ;
  parms sigma2=10 a1=1.0 a2=1.0;
  mean = a1+a2*agectsl;
  var=sigma2;
  model zwfl1 ~ normal(mean,var);
run;

/** OU TWO RANDOM EFFECTs - in MU and THETA **/
proc nlmixed data=TZ;
  parms sigma2=10 theta=9 mu=0. s2b1=1.0 cb12=1.0 s2b2=1.0;
  mu_ind=mu+b1;
  theta_ind=theta+b2;
  mean = exp((-agectsl+agectso)*theta_ind)*(zwfl0-mu_ind) + mu_ind;
  mean_marg = exp((-agectsl+agectso)*theta)*(zwfl0-mu) + mu;
  var=(exp(-2*agectsl*theta_ind)*( exp(2*agectsl*theta_ind) -exp(2*agectso*theta_ind) ) *sigma2)/(2*theta_ind);
  model zwfl1 ~ normal(mean,var);
  /*random b1 ~ normal(0,s2u) subject=subjid;*/
  random b1 b2 ~ normal([0,0],[s2b1,cb12,s2b2]) subject=subjid;
  /*predict mean_marg out=meanRV2;/** marginal residuals **/
  /*predict mean out=meanCRV2;/** conditional residuals **/
run;

/** LINEAR MIXED REGRESSION - random intercept + random slope + correlated */
proc nlmixed data=TZ;
  parms sigma2=1.0 a1=1.0 a2=1.0 s2b1=1 cb12=1.0 s2b2=1.0;
  a1_ind=a1+b1;
  a2_ind=a2+b2;
  mean = a1_ind+a2_ind*agectsl;
  mean_marg = a1+a2*agectsl;
  var=sigma2;
  model zwfl1 ~ normal(mean,var);
  random b1 b2 ~ normal([0,0],[s2b1,cb12,s2b2]) subject=subjid;
  /*predict mean_marg out=meanLinearMixed;/** marginal residuals **/
  /*predict mean out=meanCLinearMixed;/** conditional residuals **/
run;

/** Linear mixed reg */
/*proc export data=work.meanLinearMixed
  outfile='/folders/myfolders/OUfitsLinearMixed.csv'
  dbms=csv
  replace;
run;
proc export data=work.meanCLinearMixed
  outfile='/folders/myfolders/OUfitsCLinearMixed.csv'
  dbms=csv
  replace;
run;
*/
/** two random intercepts per subject in mu and theta */
/*proc export data=work.meanRV2
  outfile='/folders/myfolders/OUfitsRV2.csv'
  dbms=csv
  replace;
run;*/
/** two random intercepts per subject in mu and theta */

```

```
/*proc export data=work.meanCRV2
  outfile='/folders/myfolders/OUfitsCRV2.csv'
  dbms=csv
  replace;
run;
*/
ods html5 close;
```